

1 **The growth phenotype in RAG2^{-/-} and PRKDC^{-/-} cells can likely be attributed to activation of Xist**
2 **by DNA double strand breaks and control of Igf family gene expression by Xist.**

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11 Citations

12 1. Chiang, J.C., Jiang, J., Newburger, P.E. and Lawrence, J.B., 2018. Trisomy silencing by XIST
13 normalizes Down syndrome cell pathogenesis demonstrated for hematopoietic defects in vitro. Nature
14 communications, 9(1), p.5180.